

Mechanical behaviour of injection-moulded short glass fibre reinforced polyamide with stagnating weld-lines

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Objectives

- How do stagnating weld-lines affect the mechanical performance of PA6/GF composite?
- How do varying the injection moulding process parameters affect the strength of weld-lines?
- How can a constitutive model be developed to predict the stress-strain behaviour of samples with weld-lines?

Case Study: An injection moulded tensile bar with a stagnating weld-line

Results and Discussions

A) Weld-lines in neat PA6

- The weld-line is completely healed in the PA6 matrix.
- Weld-lines don't impact unfilled sample's mechanical strength.
- Samples are not fractured at the weld-line.

Why? The high healing ability of the PA6 matrix → Low relaxation times

T (°C)	η₀ (Pa.s)	λ (ms)
240	346	1.2
250	301	0.9
260	273	0.8

B) Weld-lines in the PA6/GF composite

>50% reduction in the tensile strength of the PA6/GF samples with weld-lines. Why? "Disturbed" fibre orientation at the WL.

Fibres are oriented in-plane when approaching the weld-line

μCT scans in the ZY plane (The scale bar in each figure shows a distance of 1 mm)

Fibre orientation: Moldflow predictions vs. Experiments

C) Effects of the processing parameters

- Increasing the packing pressure → More mechanically advantageous fibre orientations at the weld-line
- Increasing the melt temperature → Tensile strength and modulus increase and then decrease

Moldflow FOT predictions at the weld surface

Sample	270-PP40%	270-PP80%
Avg. α _{xx}	0.07	0.09
Avg. α _{yy}	0.47	0.47
Avg. α _{zz}	0.46	0.44

Underflow (backflow) during the packing phase → More favourable fibre orientations

D) The constitutive equation

Three-parameter constitutive model based on the Weibull formula:

$$\sigma = E \varepsilon \exp \left(- \left(\frac{E \varepsilon}{\sigma_0} \right)^\beta \right)$$

For finding σ_0 and β : $\ln \left[\ln \left(\frac{E \varepsilon}{\sigma} \right) \right] = \beta \ln(E \varepsilon) - \beta \ln(\sigma_0)$

- The Weibull curve's maximum predicts weld strength and fracture strain.

Conclusions

- Weld-lines in neat PA6 → completely healed
- Weld-lines in neat PA6/GF → partially healed by increasing the packing pressure
- Increasing the packing pressure → re-orienting fibres at the weld-line → increasing the weld-line strength
- The proposed equation can accurately model the tensile behaviour of the weld-lined samples

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